

THE CONCEPT OF TOURISM JOURNALISM IN MODERN UZBEKISTAN

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Today, any Internet user often comes across the term travel journalism, and we are increasingly noticing that a large number of new periodicals and television programs are appearing directly related to this branch of journalism. However, for the majority of the audience, travel journalism remains a “ghostly” concept. “Journey” in English means journey, business trip, travel. Accordingly, travel journalism is one of the media directions, the purpose of which is to inform its audience about distant countries, traditions and customs of the people, history and sights.

People began to get involved in travel long before the appearance of the phenomenon under study. As a professional activity, travel journalism took shape relatively recently and originates from the classical understanding of the Silk Road. Candidate of Historical Sciences, travel journalist N. V. Nurmatov defines the function of travel journalism as an important channel for popularizing information about other countries and peoples, their role in international communication [1].

Travel journalism researcher A.A. Burkhonov defines this phenomenon as a special area of journalism aimed at providing a mass audience with travel information, while addressing the topics of geography, tourism, history, art, ethics, culture and others.

In Uzbekistan, travel journalism on modern television occupies a separate niche. Programs of this direction are of particular interest to the viewer. Journalists working in this direction have the opportunity not only to take the viewer out of his room, but also to immerse him in a completely unpredictable and “dangerous” reality. Travel programs have their own peculiarity, they tell not only about an unusual and new world, but also about give an idea of the limits of human capabilities.

Today, modern television in Uzbekistan boasts a large number of different TV programs aimed at a wide audience: news and analytical programs, talk shows, music programs, reality shows, etc. However, there are TV programs that are aimed at a certain segment of the audience and are popular with viewers - these are programs about extreme travel. Evidence of the popularity of programs in this direction is the fact that from year to year more and more specialized channels and programs appear on modern television in Uzbekistan. In addition,

programs about extreme travels arouse ordinary curiosity among viewers and form an idea in the audience about distant countries and their peoples, about an unknown area.

Extreme travel journalism is inextricably linked with the concept of travel genre. The creators of programs of this direction in search of thrills and adrenaline go to various parts of the world. Travel journalism allows people to learn about other cultures, which is the most important thing in the context of globalization. Travel journalism, like all areas of journalism, has a number of features. One of the main features of this direction is the specific structure and dramaturgy of the travel text. Despite the fact that the viewer can see with his own eyes what the journalist himself saw, the off-screen text is of great importance for sensory perception [3].

Thanks to programs of this orientation, the viewer has the opportunity, without leaving his room, to receive a charge of vivid emotions. Therefore, viewers are always waiting for new programs related to extreme travel. "In the very concept of the extreme as a phenomenon that stands out from the general background, out of the ordinary, there is a huge potential for television production. Therefore, today's television is rapidly developing an extreme direction, diversifying the genre and thematic palette of "adrenaline" programs" [2].

Extreme TV today occupies a strong position in the TV broadcast grid. It is not for nothing that extreme television researchers call it "adrenaline-packed" television. This is due to the programs that are broadcast within the framework of this television always look "spectacular" because the viewer has the opportunity to get a large dose of adrenaline along with the host of the program. "These emotions caused by an extreme situation turn on the endocrine system, releasing adrenaline into the blood, or, as it is also called, the hormone of action." Journalists of Uzbekistan in their programs introduce us not only to the journey of world countries, but also to travel through the regions and cities of Uzbekistan, encouraging viewers to boldly travel and be alone with the beauties of places.

Journalists working on travel programs such as extreme trawling are in danger: they find themselves on a frozen volcano, descending mountain cliffs without the necessary equipment, passing through narrow caves and do not always know what awaits them behind this or that obstacle.

The famous Australian television journalist and expert on working with predatory animals, Steve Irwin, has never been in such situations in which serious harm could be done to his health. In his program "The Crocodile Hunter",

he not only talked about reptiles, but also had close contact with them. Despite his great experience with such animals, he was not completely protected from their aggression and there were cases when snakes and crocodiles bit him. Although extreme journalists act according to a pre-written scenario, the conditions in which they work do not always obey their plans. They cannot fully predict what "surprises" nature has prepared for them, or how wild animals will behave when they come into close contact with a person.

Every TV journalist involved in this or that type of hobby seeks to get pleasure that cannot be compared with anything. To do this, he is ready to overcome all the difficulties and dangers associated with the risk to life. A person for whom traveling or doing extreme sports is a hobby, after watching such TV shows, gets excited. He learns about new places that have attracted his attention, and, as a result, makes up his route in order, first, to prove to himself that he is capable of doing this or that act and setting his own sports record.

Extreme travel journalism requires media representatives to have certain psychological and physical skills. Extreme travel journalists need to be emotionally stable, physically fit, and fully aware of what they will be doing.

Journalists have a difficult task not only to give an idea of their audience about a particular country, but also to entertain it. Despite the difficulties in creating travel programs, a large number of new programs on this topic appear on modern television from year to year.

Summing up, it is worth noting that there is no definition of travel journalism fixed in the scientific discourse. Based on our own experience of researching empirical material, we can give the following definition: travel journalism is a special direction in journalism that specializes in providing information about travel and sports, touching on the topics of geography, history, cultural heritage, and is directly related to the activities of journalists.

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